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Challenges for teaching sustainability and promoting diversity within a software engineering course

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ABSTRACT

This report covers the challenges of integrating sustainability into the curricula of an undergraduate module for software engineering students and ensuring an inclusive and research based learning environment. Making skills audits explicit to team members provided a mechanism to help identify topics students wanted to learn and skills they needed for their projects. These audits particularly identified females' interests in sustainability and a chance to collaborate more widely, which helped identify a suitable research project and industry partner. Ensuring that there were no lone females in any project team necessitated larger groups, requiring more detailed attention to team structure and communications but provided greater opportunities for students to develop knowledge in areas that they wished. Documenting skills and discussing the different views of stakeholders: potential users of the software product, team members, industry teams and research groups across the university, also provided an appreciation of the value of diversity. Integrating projects that cover the topics female students have identified has provided a path for increasing sustainability education within the curricula and provided opportunities to pursue their interests. Experience suggests larger agile research teams may provide a route to supporting women in engineering and developing their potential in leadership.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Gender and Diversity, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: sustainability, software engineering, women in engineering, diversity

INTRODUCTION

There has been a continuing problem for years of under-representation of females in STEM subjects [1]. This paper outlines the challenges in addressing this issue while also trying to ensure sustainability is integral to the curricula of a technology management module and aligned to the humanitarian objectives of the university and UN Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) [2]. Identifying student's interests and aspirations helped develop a suitable undergraduate research project, as well as

create an improved understanding of each team member's goals. Detailed skills audits (see section 2.1) clarified students' interests; brought to the fore female students' interests in wider topics within their subject, particularly regarding sustainability and opportunities to collaborate, and male students' interests in developing a complete solution. Working in larger teams not only gave individuals a greater opportunity to work on topics they wanted to learn, but also facilitated a supportive environment and an understanding that diversity enhances teamwork and research.

1 BACKGROUND

Improving diversity in engineering enhances creating solutions that inherently meet the needs of the wider population, not just solutions based on a narrow range of perspectives [3]. Improving diversity also aids innovation, the economic success of organisations, addresses the engineering skills shortage and contributes to creating a fairer society [3], [4]. University College London (UCL), Faculty of Engineering Sciences is dedicated to promoting diversity and increasing the number of women within engineering careers. The Department of Computer Science, within this faculty, has gained recognition for initiatives to support women in engineering in achieving an Athena Swan Silver award [5].

This paper covers the technology management module for final year undergraduate computer science students for the academic year 2015/16. This module is now integrated into other engineering courses. It covers the experience of ensuring research-based projects, problem-based learning (PBL) [6] and curricula are in line with the recommendations of professional bodies and leading engineering education reviews [7], [8] and content is co-evolved with students. To avoid gender bias and sole females in project teams, larger sized groups were required. This created the need for more detailed attention to boundary communications [9], how the teams were split along architectural lines and a focus on industry team structures and their approaches to acknowledging each team member's contribution.

There is recognition that organisations need to attract what Eric Schmidt, chief executive of Alphabet, and the holding organization of Google terms "learning animals"; employees who want to embrace life-long learning, willingness to continually learn new technologies and processes [10]. The wider social and teamwork skills are often just as important, if not more so [6] if we are going to develop the necessary collaborative skills needed in research and business.

Highlighting problems from other cities around the world helped engage students from the diverse cultures within the class and helped them appreciate that the research is aimed at solving a global problem. The project was placed in context of the UN sustainable development goals and the sustainable initiatives of the university, UCL Grand Challenges [11].

Students during the previous academic year had delivered research projects in the form of apps to enhance bicycle hire provision [12]. This theme of sustainable living continued for projects for the year 2015/16. Each team were encouraged to develop a solution of their own choice that would suggest routes or areas with lower levels of air pollution for those walking or cycling in London. Students were given the option to suggest an alternative project, to facilitate a more sustainable future and improve health and were encouraged to seek feedback from the intended users of their app as well as from an appropriate industry partner.

2 CHALLENGES

2.1 Integrating sustainability into the curriculum

Understanding of what students wanted to learn was gathered via feedback, retrospectives and project reviews. An in-depth understanding of goals and aspirations helped all team members and tutors understand what each individual wanted to achieve, what they could contribute and what they wanted to learn and helped everyone appreciate each other's skills. Subjects identified from female students' feedback included: sustainability, opportunities to collaborate and an emphasis on the wider aspects of computing. Feedback from male students included technical interests, relating to building data-intensive applications and behaviour driven development (BDD). Integrating the needs of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) within a crowded curriculum was a challenge. Sustainability is a contested concept. However, there is general agreement according to Hasse [13], that it covers social, environmental and economic concerns. In addition, Haase considers that the different perspectives and models may help students develop the necessary critical pedagogic experience to understand different stakeholders' viewpoints.

2.2 Integrating the interests of female students

Studies of female students show a higher percentage participation in health and medical technologies, design, and biotechnology [14]. As feedback and skills audits from this module, indicated that female students were interested in pollution and health, it was agreed that students would be encouraged to develop apps to reduce exposure to air pollution. For this course feedback from female students also indicated that opportunities to work collaboratively in projects aligned to industry and sustainability were important issues. So it would seem logical to assume that courses with a focus on projects that overlap these interests may enhance the participation of female students.

2.3 Ensuring females are supported by their peers

In discussing STEM self-concept, Simpkins et al., [15] have considered how one's belief in one's abilities, based on the perception of others, can affect pedagogic outcomes. Rachael Robnett [16], outlines evidence that gender bias is antecedent to self-concept [17]. Robnett further highlights evidence that bias often originates from male peers, and this is further exacerbated in fields where females are severely underrepresented. To this end, to ensure a reduction in gender bias and that there were no lone females, an issue of concern highlighted by Beddoes [18], the class was split into 6 teams, of either 13 or 14 students, ensuring at least two females in each team. Eccles and Wigfield [19] suggest that ensuring that females are supported via their peers and teachers can improve their self-concept and that ensuring support by mentors would enhance this further. Female students were therefore encouraged to select someone they considered supportive from another team, to help with retrospectives.

Where research goals are clarified and females have their peers' affirmation, the development of effective team building skills necessary for engineering projects is enhanced [20]. Also, aligning the goals to the values of peers and society, the perceived value of the research is likely to be raised. As the problems associated with air pollution are a societal concern, all teams considered that opportunities to create an app to reduce exposure were an opportunity to create something

worthwhile, learn new skills, and engage with research initiatives across the university covering sustainable cities.

The lecturers were invited to have access to team online project areas, in contrast to making this a course requirement in previous years. This seemed to create more openness over project issues as well as approaches to resolve problems. As *Table 1* shows, the percentage of communications initiated by females were higher than would be expected from the percentage representation within their teams. (Tools selected by students included: Trello, Slack, Jira, GoogleHangouts and Microsoft Visual Team Studio.)

Table 1. The data shown for two project teams, tracking just one of their software communication tools, Trello, within project weeks 2 to 6. Teams A and B both consisted of 3 female and 11 male students. (Letters have been substituted for actual project names for anonymity.)

Project Team	Number of communications tracked	Number of female initiated communications	% female within project team	% female initiated communications
A	112	60	21	54
B	102	56	21	55

As in previous years, females were encouraged and supported in taking on leadership roles for projects, as advocated within WISE publications [21]. Female students considered the structures and being allowed to elicit support from their peers during retrospectives helped them to contribute and develop their project management skills.

“Being the first practical insight I had into the Agile Methodology, this project enabled me to grow from a management, teamwork and leadership perspective. Throughout the development process, I seriously improved my self-discipline, which was crucial in order to properly manage my team to success.” (Female student)

Challenge 2.4 Initial concern regarding team size

The opportunity to work in a larger team than students had previously experienced during their studies created an initial concern for one team. Students mentioned that they had not experienced these large groups before, and were concerned that they would only have a limited time to get to know one another. With students asking for advice how to split teams and plan communications, team structure examples were outlined; covering “Inverse Conway’s Manoeuvre” [22] ensuring the team structure reflects and supports the architecture of the app, and also boundary communications with sub-teams and their industry collaborators.

3. DISCUSSION

To ensure student-centred learning “flipped lectures” were adopted, providing key research papers the week before discussing these in class and considering how findings could be applied to their projects.

The Adair model was introduced as outlined by Braun and colleagues [23], with an explanation that this is often used in industry as a framework for skills audits: what skills individuals need to develop, what skills the team require, what skills are

necessary for the project. Students were encouraged to view this not as a static document but as a tool to help identify the necessary skills throughout the project, as well as self-appraisal, sub-team and project appraisal at the end of the project.

From audits, class questions and project reviews, it was apparent that all students were keen to link these to the UCL Grand Challenges. Male students were particularly keen to build working apps, as one commented: “from beginning to end”. Not surprisingly, as this was a computing module, virtually all skills audit comments, including those from female students, covered their wish to improve their software development skills and machine learning techniques.

“As a member of the research team, I also got the chance to work on something that I have long planned to learn, R programming. Working together with ... we implemented 3 models for NO₂, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ ... but also learn more things about linear regressions and hypothesis testing.” (Female student)

Working prototype apps, reports, and videos were delivered within 9 weeks. All project teams elicited feedback from: industry partners, potential users and the class, to improve designs and digital accessibility of their prototypes. Apps are being currently developed further by organisations, such as the London Sustainability Exchange (LSx) [24] a not for profit community-based organisation, set-up to enhance the sustainability of London. All teams expressed positive views that they had the opportunity to produce something tangible to improve sustainability and provide an opportunity for those living in cities to lower their exposure to air pollution.

Rogojanu and Badea outline that ESD encapsulates an attitude to the environment and ethical aspects [25]. One team negotiated a slightly different focus for their project, based on estimating the pollution level residents may be exposed to for properties available for rental or sale. They developed an air pollution app to be incorporated within the website of the online property sales and rental organisation they were collaborating with. During prototype discussions in class, the team outlined the dilemmas faced, with uncertainty whether properties associated with high levels of pollutants will actually have air quality data shown on the property website. These discussions were invaluable in helping students appreciate the ethics associated with sustainable engineering solutions and the perspectives of different stakeholders.

The course integrated the technology with coverage of technology management with an emphasis on communication and design decisions. Detailed investigations of the data sets and the different viewpoints of the designs from potential users, industry partners and other researchers at UCL also provided a range of improvements. One team utilised traffic noise open data, as an effective proxy measure for air pollutants. Recording design decisions and alternatives also supported the ethos of the course considering opinions from all stakeholders.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

It has been shown by EU sponsored surveys [26] that females are more concerned with air pollution than males. Carefully selecting related engineering projects may, therefore, help promote engagement and increase numbers from female students. Kolmos et al., [14] have indicated that female engagement may be further encouraged by interaction with female professional engineers in the workplace. It was noticeable that students had specific interests during this project, covering technical areas, sustainability or ethics. Female students showed a particular interest

in sustainability topics, which were integrated throughout the course. Male students showed specific interests in application development, such as the node.js platform, and coding approaches that could be understood by both technical and business users. The nexus of interests, from both genders, aided collaboration with industry partners and ensured engagement with this research from all teams. This also provides further opportunities to track students' engagement, whatever their initial interests, and ensures that their progression and development of skills for each category of interest are met. This is particularly important if we are to further improve diversity and inclusion initiatives.

We need to consider how students learn in a more holistic way and consider students' methods of learning, including cognitive and affective [27]. The project structures allowed teams to work in an environment of psychological safety and the opportunity to ask for support during retrospectives increased openness and encouraged a higher level of participation, especially from female students. An inclusive environment was further fostered, by encouraging students to support their peers and join specific support groups at UCL [28].

Research papers often point to small team size covering agile software practices [29]. However, further understanding of optimal team size for education is an area of research that needs investigation, especially as there is a trend in technology organisations to adopt larger team sizes [30]. This also created a need for more detailed peer assessments to show the contributions of individuals and what the project would have been like without their support. The larger size of the project teams, compared to other courses in the department, allowed for specialism and ensured there were no "token" females in each group.

"By working on the project with the big team, it makes me realize how we can manage the project and team relationship effectively using sprint iterations." (Female student)

"Comparing with my previous teamwork and team lead experiences, I noticed a fair improvement of my time management and planning skills. This was mostly due to the fact that I learnt to rely on others, instead of taking care of every issue myself. Although I am a perfectionist through nature, the complexity of this project forced me to pass over responsibilities to the Point Persons [responsible for the task]." (Female student)

Teams were encouraged to develop detailed skills audits, which created the opportunity to identify the knowledge and skills individuals wanted to learn and share, and recognition that everyone has something valuable to contribute. Many students considered they had developed a better understanding of complex sustainability issues from consideration of the different viewpoints from potential users of their app, industry partners and other research groups within the university. Discussions regarding the interpretation of pollution and health data, software architecture decisions and approaches to software development and communications also helped them gain a better appreciation of the value of diversity, and that everyone brings valuable experiences and skills to a team.

"We all have different backgrounds, different personalities, different habits and different ways of working. I learnt to enjoy the differences in our cultures and respect one another." (Female student)

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REFERENCES

- [1] IET (2017), Progressing women in STEM roles
<http://www.theiet.org/policy/collaboration/stem/index.cfm>
[Accessed: 21 April 2017]
- [2] United Nations (2012), Future We Want, United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development, paragraph 233, Rio+20, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, June 2012 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/rio20/futurewewant>
[Accessed: 20 March 2017]
- [3] Rossi, B. (2017), A platform for diversity, editor's letter, Information Age January 2017, and *The Business of Diversity*, Information Age, January 2017, pp. 31-33.
- [4] Shapiro, C.A. & Sax, L.J. (2011), Major selection and persistence for women in STEM, *New Directions for Institutional Research*, vol. 152, pp. 5-18.
- [5] UCL Engineering (2016), Athena Swan Silver Award for Computer Science, May, 2016
<https://www.engineering.ucl.ac.uk/news/10575-2/> [Accessed: 20 April 2017]
- [6] Guerra, A. (2017), "Integration of sustainability in engineering education: Why is PBL an answer?", *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, Vol. 18, Issue. 3, pp. 436-454.
- [7] Shadbolt, N. (2016), Review of Computer Sciences Degree Accreditation and Graduate Employability, April 2016
https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/518575/ind-16-5-shadbolt-review-computer-science-graduate-employability.pdf [Accessed: 20 April 2017]
- [8] Computer Science Curricula (2013), Curriculum Guidelines for Undergraduate Degree Programs in Computer Science, Professional Practice, p15, ACM/IEEE Computer Society
<http://www.acm.org/education/CS2013-final-report.pdf>
[Accessed: 20 April 2017]
- [9] Strode, D.E., Huff, S.L., Hope, B. & Link, S. (2012), Co-ordination in co-located agile software development projects, *The Journal of Systems and Software*, vol.85, pp. 1222-1238.
- [10] Economist special report (2017), Learning and Earning: Cognition switch, print edition, 14th January, 2017
<http://www.economist.com/news/special-report/21714171-companies-are-embracing-learning-core-skill-what-employers-can-do-encourage-their>
- [11] UCL Grand Challenges, <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/grand-challenges>
- [12] UCL (2015) Computer Science News,
http://www.cs.ucl.ac.uk/computer_science_news/article/ucl-welcomes-top-software-engineers-from-nii-tokyo/ [Accessed: 6 February 2017]
- [13] Haase, S. (2014), Engineering students' sustainability approaches, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, vol. 39(3), pp. 247-271.
- [14] Kolmos, A., Mejlgaard, N., Haase, S., & Holgaard, J.E. (2013), Motivational factors, gender and engineering education, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, vol. 38(3), pp. 340-358.

- [15] Simpkins, S. D., Davis-Kean, P. E., & Eccles, J. S. (2006), Math and science motivation: A longitudinal examination of the links between choices and beliefs. *Developmental Psychology*, vol. 42(1), pp. 70–83.
- [16] Robnett, R. (2016), Gender Bias in STEM Fields: Variation in Prevalence and Links to STEM, Self-Concept, *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 2016, Vol. 40(1), pp. 65-79.
- [17] Brown, C.S. & Leaper, C. (2010), Latina and European American girls' experiences with academic racism and their self-concepts in mathematics and science adolescence, *Sex Roles*, vol. 63, pp. 860-870.
- [18] Beddoes, K. (2015), Professors' Perceptions of How Men and Women Students Experience Engineering Education Differently...Or Not, *European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) 2015 Proceedings Annual Conference*, Orleans, France.
- [19] Eccles, J.S. & Wigfield, A. (2002), Motivational Beliefs and Goals, *Annual Review of Psychology*, vol. 53, pp.109-32.
- [20] Riney, M.R. & Froeschle, J. (2012), Socialization Processes of Engineering Students: Differences in the Experiences of Females and Males, *Administrative Issues Journal: Education, Practice, and Research*, Vol. 2(1), pp. 96-106.
- [21] Jordan, J. (2011), Women into leadership: how to encourage women into leadership roles in science, engineering and technology, The UKRC, <https://www.wisecampaign.org.uk/resources/2011/02/women-into-leadership-how-to-encourage-women-into-leadership-roles-in-science-engineering-and-technology> [Accessed: 7 March 2017]
- [22] <https://www.thoughtworks.com/radar/techniques/inverse-conway-maneuver> [Accessed: 6 February 2017]
- [23] Braun, F.C., Avital, M. & Martz, B. (2012), Action-centred team leadership influences more than performance, *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*, vol. 18(3/4), pp. 176-195.
- [24] <http://www.lsx.org.uk> [Accessed: 21 April 2017]
- [25] Rogojanu, A. and Badea, L. (2011), Business Ethics and Education –an Intelligent Solution or a Sustainable Development? *Equilibrium*, vol. 6 (4), pp. 21-37.
- [26] EU Flash Eurobarometer 360 Report (2013), Attitudes of Europeans Towards Air Quality, European Commission, July 2013. http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/flash/fl_360_en.pdf [Accessed: 20 April 2017]
- [27] Gazibara, S. (2013), "“Head, Heart and Hands Learning” - A challenge for contemporary education". *The Journal of Education, Culture, and Society*, vol. 1(1), pp. 71-82.
- [28] UCL Women in Computer Science <http://www.cs.ucl.ac.uk/wics/home/> [Accessed: 20 April 2017]
- [29] Vlietland, J. & Vliet van, H. (2015), Towards a governance framework for chains of Scrum teams, *Information and Software Technology*, Vol. 57, pp. 52-65.
- [30] Murgia, M. (2017), *Free Thinkers: Ideas rather than products are the focus at this artificial intelligence company*, Drivers of Change Deep Mind, Boldness in Business report, Financial Times, pp. 20-23, March 2017 <https://www.ft.com/content/cada14c4-d366-11e6-b06b-680c49b4b4c0> [Accessed: 20 April 2017]